

The Activities of the First Printing Houses in Uzbekistan and its Development and Significance Today

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ABSTRACT: This article discusses the activities of the first printing houses in Uzbekistan and their significance today. In the East, the book has long been valued. For, in the eyes of the peoples of the East, it is not only an ointment of hearts, but also a burial of secrets, a sea of treasures, a mine of sciences, a source of sages, a piece of nobility. From the cover of the book to the art of calligraphy, patterned ornaments and miniatures, everything is poetically pleasing to the eye, pleasing to the heart and pleasing to the soul.

KEYWORDS: printing houses, East, book, hearts, secrets, treasures, sciences, sages, calligraphy, miniatures, soul.

INTRODUCTION

After the independence of our country, the attention to art has increased, and its role in the socio-economic spheres, as well as in spiritual education has been given great importance. Art is essentially an important process that is able to influence a person's emotions. Professor Abdurauf Fitrat, a well-known Jadid thinker, knew that art is "producing something well". Fitrat, reflecting on art and its impact on human, said: a person who sees a great joy increases his joy by expressing his feelings of joy to others. Every event in existence becomes an object of further enjoyment by human. However, in this process, spirituality and reality become the main criteria.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Only in this way does the harmonization of cultures create the dignity of universal culture and the beauty of the whole civilization. For a common civilization is formed from the cultures of different peoples. The world-famous Russian writer Islam Karimov, the first President of Uzbekistan, changed F. Dostoevsky's logical phrase "Beauty saves the world" to "culture and spirituality will save the world in the 21st century"[1].

After the independence of Uzbekistan, there was a dramatic change in publishing. The legal basis in this regard was the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Publishing" (August 30, 1996). According to the law, publishers will be able to work independently in their activities, including the direction of publication, topics, specialization, copy of the product, the choice of author. Legal entities and individuals have the right to engage in publishing activities after state registration and obtaining a license in the manner prescribed by law. Censorship of manuscripts and materials prepared for publication was abolished. Publishers began to try to publish books that were in demand due to the demands of a market economy. They were given complete freedom in determining the content of book products. Due to the granting of the status of the state language to the Uzbek language, the weight of books in the Uzbek language has increased. Many books on the subject of Amir Temur, great thinkers, religious and national values have been published. In particular, a 33-volume book "Memory" was published in Tashkent publishing houses. Uzbekistan Publishing House has published multi-volume works by the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov.

Prior to the establishment of the printing house in Tashkent, the work of the secretary and calligraphers played an important role in the preparation of the book. In Tashkent, Abdulvadud katib (15th-16th centuries), Abdulhaq katib (1808-1886), Muhammad Yunus katib (19th century), Abdulmannop katib (1880-1945), Muhammad Shahmurad katib (1850-1922), Siddiqi Khandayliqi (1884-1934) and others. In Tashkent, they developed the art of bookmaking - the creation, copying and embellishment of manuscripts.

The emergence of book publishing in Tashkent. Printing in Tashkent began in the second half of the 19th century, after the invasion of Turkestan by Tsarist Russia. The first printing house in Tashkent was established in 1868 at the headquarters of the Turkestan military district, which published the first printed book in Russian - the work of Russian scientist N.A. Severtsov, who studied the fauna, geography and geology of Central Asia.

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After that, Tashkent became the center of book publishing in Central Asia. 1871 The first printed book in the Uzbek language (mainly intended for traders) - Sh. Ibrahimov's book "Calendar" was published in the Arabic alphabet. It was during this period that private printing presses also began to appear: V.F. Pastukhov printing house (firm "Lakhtin and Pastukhov" since 1876, 1878, typography of S.I. Lakhtin since 1880), I. Husanbaev (1883), O.A. Portsev (1888), F.H. Orifjonov (1889), M. Bekmuhamedov (1908), I. Inogomjanov (1914) and others. They publish fiction and educational literature in Uzbek and Russian languages.

In March 1920, the Turkestan State Publishing House was established in Tashkent. It was the first book publishing house in Central Asia to coordinate all publishing work in the country, oversee the distribution and management of paper and printing equipment.

In Tashkent, too, calligraphy took a long time, and even after the invention of printing, books were first copied by hand in Tashkent. At the National Library of present-day Uzbekistan, a group of calligraphers was engaged in the reproduction of manuscripts before World War II. After the establishment of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan in 1943, qualified calligraphers from the library (Ibodulla Adilov, Abdukodir Murodov, Abdulla Nosirov, Usmon Karimov) transferred to the institute, where they restored, copied and compiled descriptions of unique manuscripts. By the 1980s, especially after the independence of Uzbekistan, book art began to be revived as a work of art. Habibulla Salih, Abdulla Mirsoatov, Salimjon Badalboev, Tukhtamurod Zufarov, Alisher Shomammedov and others have done a great job in this.

The intricate relationship between the artist and the book creator that binds his work goes back centuries with its depth. The inscriptions created in ancient times still amaze us. In the East, the book has long been valued. For, in the eyes of the peoples of the East, it is not only an ointment of hearts, but also a burial of secrets, a sea of treasures, a mine of sciences, a source of sages, a piece of nobility. From the cover of the book to the art of calligraphy, patterned ornaments and miniatures, everything is poetic, to the delight of the eyes, to the heart, to the soul. New features have appeared in the art of Uzbek book graphics. The originality of the artists' work was obvious. They began to appear with their signatures, of course, their favorite style, their interest in a particular subject. They began to make extensive use of a variety of decorating tools, from font to plot image.

CONCLUSION

In short, the emergence of the first printing houses in Uzbekistan is directly related to the activities of calligraphers and graphic artists. In this regard, the artists fought for the unity of all the elements in the book's graphics. The appearance of the book began to be bright and colorful. Along with the colorful images, the number of pictures drawn on the page within the text has also increased. In short, it was decided to look at the book as a whole "ensemble".

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